

Original Article

Publication History:

Published 20/10/2020

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4244790

Corresponding Author:

Dr. Sajid Zaheer, DHQ
Teaching Hospital
Gujranwala,
sajidzaheer1994@gmail.com

Cite this article as:

Khan A, Zahid A, Zaheer S.
Trends of postgraduation
among medical doctors.
Int. J. Med. Dent. Allied
Health Sci. 2020;2(10).
367-71

© Copyright 2020

This is an open access article
distributed under the terms of the
Creative Commons Attribution
License CC-BY 4.0., which
permits unrestricted use,
distribution, and reproduction in
any medium, provided the
original author and source are
credited.

**TRENDS OF POSTGRADUATION AMONG
MEDICAL DOCTORS**

AUTHORS:

1. DR. AHMAD KHAN, DHQ TEACHING HOSPITAL
GUJRANWALA
2. DR. AQSA ZAHID, DHQ TEACHING HOSPITAL
GUJRANWALA
3. DR. SAJID ZAHEER, DHQ TEACHING HOSPITAL
GUJRANWALA

ABSTRACT:

Medical education is education related to the practice of being a medical practitioner, including the initial training to become a physician (i.e., medical school and house job) and additional training thereafter (e.g., residency, fellowship and continuing medical education). This cross-sectional study was conducted among the medical doctors doing their house jobs or who have just completed their house jobs. All the doctors were served with a predefined questionnaire. Different questions about their field of interest, plan for postgraduation were asked. A total of 98 medical doctors participated in this study. Out of 98 participants, 78 returned the proforma. The response rate was 79.60%. There were 23 female doctors and 55 male doctors. Fifty-six doctors were not sure about their postgraduation. The reasons were the uncertainty about the merit policies, lack of postgraduation seats and some doctors were also lacking the details of different postgraduation degrees. Twenty-two doctors had focused their degrees and were preparing for those exams accordingly.

Keywords: Medical Education, Postgraduation

INTRODUCTION:

Medical education is education related to the practice of being a medical practitioner, including the initial training to become a physician (i.e., medical school and house job) and additional training thereafter (e.g., residency, fellowship and continuing medical education). Medical education and training vary considerably across the world. Various teaching methodologies have been used in medical education, which is an active area of educational research. Medical education is also the subject-didactic academic field of educating medical doctors at all levels, including entry-level, post-graduate, and continuing medical education. Medical education applies theories of pedagogy specifically in the context of medical education. Specific requirements such as entrustable professional activities must be met before moving on in stages of medical education.

Medical education is increasingly utilizing online teaching, usually within learning management systems (LMSs) or virtual learning environments (VLEs). Additionally, several medical schools

have incorporated the use of blended learning combining the use of video, asynchronous, and in-person exercises. A landmark scoping review published in 2018 demonstrated that online teaching modalities are becoming increasingly prevalent in medical education, with associated high student satisfaction and improvement on knowledge tests. However, the use of evidence-based multimedia design principles in the development of online lectures was seldom reported, despite their known effectiveness in medical student contexts. To enhance variety in an online delivery environment, the use of serious games, which have previously shown benefit in medical education, can be incorporated to break the monotony of online-delivered lectures.

Research areas into online medical education include practical applications, including simulated patients and virtual medical records. When compared to no intervention, simulation in medical education training is associated with positive effects on knowledge, skills, and behaviors and moderate effects for patient outcomes. However, data is inconsistent on the effectiveness of

asynchronous online learning when compared to traditional in-person lectures. Furthermore, studies utilizing modern visualization technology (i.e. virtual and augmented reality) have shown great promise as means to supplement lesson content in physiological and anatomical education.

Following completion of entry-level training, newly graduated doctors are often required to undertake a period of supervised practice before full registration is granted; this is most often of one-year duration and may be referred to as an house job or provisional registration. Further training in a particular field of medicine may be undertaken. In Pakistan, further specialized training, completed after residency is referred to as fellowship. In most countries, continuing medical education (CME) courses are required for continued licensing. CME requirements vary by state and by country. Physicians often attend dedicated lectures, grand rounds, conferences, and performance improvement activities in order to fulfill their requirements. Additionally, physicians are increasingly opting to

pursue further graduate-level training in the formal study of medical education as a pathway for continuing professional development (1-4).

Material of Methods:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among the medical doctors doing their house jobs or who have just completed their house jobs. All the doctors were served with a predefined questionnaire. Different questions about their field of interest, plan for postgraduation were asked. The confidentiality of the respondents was assured. All the data was entered and analyzed on SPSS Ver. 23.0. The qualitative variables were presented as numbers and percentages. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviations.

RESULTS:

A total of 98 medical doctors participated in this study. Out of 98 participants, 78 returned the proforma. The response rate was 79.60%. There were 23 female doctors and 55 male doctors. Fifty-six doctors were not sure about their postgraduation. The reasons were the uncertainty about the merit policies, lack of postgraduation seats

and some doctors were also lacking the details of different postgraduation degrees. Twenty-two doctors had focused their degrees and were preparing for those exams accordingly.

DISCUSSION:

As medical professional stakeholders in the field of health care, the practice of medicine (i.e. diagnosing, treating, and monitoring disease) is directly affected by the ongoing changes in both national and local health policy and economics.

There is a growing call for health professional training programs to not only adopt more rigorous health policy education and leadership training, but to apply a broader lens to the concept of teaching and implementing health policy through health equity and social disparities that largely affect health and patient outcomes. Increased mortality and morbidity rates occur from birth to age 75, attributed to medical care (insurance access, quality of care), individual behavior (smoking, diet, exercise, drugs, risky behavior), socioeconomic and demographic factors (poverty, inequality, racial disparities, segregation), and physical environment (housing, education, transportation,

urban planning). A country's health care delivery system reflects its "underlying values, tolerances, expectations, and cultures of the societies they serve", and medical professionals stand in a unique position to influence opinion and policy of patients, healthcare administrators, & lawmakers (5-6).

REFERENCES:

1. Iobst WF, Sherbino J, Cate OT, Richardson DL, Dath D, Swing SR, Harris P, Mungroo R, Holmboe ES, Frank JR, International CBME Collaborators. Competency-based medical education in postgraduate medical education. *Medical teacher*. 2010 Aug 1;32(8):651-6.
2. Harden RM. Trends and the future of postgraduate medical education. *Emergency Medicine Journal*. 2006 Oct 1;23(10):798-802.
3. Smits PB, D de Buissonjé C, Verbeek JH, van Dijk FJ, Metz JC, Cate OJ. Problem-based learning versus lecture-based learning in postgraduate medical education. *Scandinavian journal of work, environment & health*. 2003 Aug 1:280-7.
4. Moonesinghe SR, Lowery J, Shahi N, Millen A, Beard JD. Impact of reduction in working hours for doctors in training on postgraduate medical education and patients' outcomes: systematic review. *Bmj*. 2011 Mar 22;342.

International Journal of Medical, Dental, and Allied Health Sciences

5. Sethi A, Schofield S, Ajjawi R, McAleer S. How do postgraduate qualifications in medical education impact on health professionals?. *Medical teacher*. 2016 Feb 1;38(2):162-7.
6. Busing N, Harris K, MacLellan AM, Moineau G, Oandasan I, Rourke J, Saxena A. The future of postgraduate medical education in Canada. *Academic Medicine*. 2015 Sep 1;90(9):1258-63.